

Agri Tech Startups in India: An Analysis of VUCA

Rashmi R¹, Dr. S Rosaline Jayanthi²

¹Research Scholar, St Francis De Sales college, Electronic City, Bangalore.

²Assistant Professor, St Francis De Sales college, Electronic City, Bangalore.

Abstract:

The agri-tech sector in India is burgeoning, driven by technological advancements and a growing need for innovative solutions in agriculture. However, this dynamic environment is characterized by Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity (VUCA), which pose significant challenges to startups in this field. This study aims to explore how VUCA factors impact agri-tech startups in India, focusing on their operational strategies, adaptability, and overall resilience.

The research employs a descriptive approach, including study of secondary data. Key objectives include identifying the primary VUCA-related challenges faced by these startups, evaluating their strategic responses, and analysing them through the stage of the Start-ups. Additionally, the study examines the role of external factors such as government policies, institutional support, and market conditions in shaping the startups' ability to navigate a VUCA landscape.

The research provides actionable insights for entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers, offering recommendations to improve strategic planning and resource allocation in the face of VUCA. By understanding and addressing the impact of VUCA, stakeholders can better support the growth and sustainability of agri-tech startups in India, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and innovative agricultural sector.

Keywords: Agri tech startups, VUCA

Introduction:

Agri-tech start-ups, we are in technological improvement where advancement of agriculture has adopted advanced innovations using technology. Agriculture is the backbone of the country. The words tell our land is equipped with agriculture produce since history. Start-ups are the introductory stage of the product to the market. Agri-tech start-ups are the involvement of entrepreneurship in technologically advanced agriculture.

As per the Start-up database as on 31st December 2023, there are 2800 Agri-tech start-ups in India. Sustainability is emerging in all aspects of the economy. Agri-tech start-ups ensure the sustainability goals to be achieved. Traditional agriculture has problems related to weather, pests control, food safety, supply chain. These problems are being observed and treated with the technologically equipped start-ups. Agri-tech start-ups involve IOT [Internet of Things], AI[Artificial Intelligence], Big data analytics, Precision farming, Supply chain, Drones and automation. The integration of technology has provided solutions for various traditional agricultural problems. The agri-tech start-ups are facing challenges for

the setup, establishment and sustainability. The issues of start-ups are being addressed by government with various policies and initiatives.

Review of literature:

National

Startups in India, a study on challenges and prospects of selected units in Bengaluru (Geethanjali) has studied the role of startups in India, its contribution to the ecosystem. The study is analysed through the hypothesis testing for each objective. Different quantitative metrics like Chi-square and ANOVA were performed to analyse the data with regard to challenges faced by startups, the impact of the startup ecosystem on startups and the role played by the Startuppreneurs. The behavior of the entrepreneurs towards career is positive.

Agri-tech Startups: The Ray of Hope in Indian Agriculture (MANAGE, 2019) has given the study of startups which is rising in the 21st century followed by agri tech startups. The discussion analyses the importance of agri tech startups. The two cities of south india- Bangalore and Hyderabad are studied with the leading agri tech startups based on their establishment and turnover.

Research Article Challenges and Opportunities for Agri- Tech Startups in developing economies (Bethi and Deshmukh) has studied The challenges for agri tech startups being- Technology adoption, funding and investment, skill and capacity building, infrastructure, market access and supply chain integration. The opportunities being innovation to new technology, access to new networks, Public private partnerships, education and awareness and policy implications. The study is a descriptive study to analyse the opportunities and challenges faced by the Indian agri tech startups.

Agri-tech Start-ups: Revolutionizing the Agricultural Value Chain in India (Sanjiv Kumar, Ranjit Kumar , K. Srinivas and Alok Kumar 2022) has studied the statistics of total startups in India being 99, 604 among which agri tech startups are 1293. The stages of agri tech startups are also explained. Greater number of IOT and sensor based startups are sensitised.

Agri-tech startups Redefining Indian agriculture (Shailesh Palab) has analysed the incubators and accelerators for the agri tech startups in the current scenario. Ninjacart is a Bangalore based largest Fresh Produce Supply Chain Company of India founded in 2015. By optimizing the supply chain and removing multiple layers of middlemen, the company is reducing the operational cost and transferring benefits to farmers while making produce cheaper to end customers. Currently, Supply Chain is equipped to move 1400 tonnes of perishables from farms to businesses, every day, in less than 12 hours. Company received a funding of INR 250Cr. in 2018 and revenue of 132 Cr. in 2018-19

Agri-tech Startups in India: A Revolutionary Idea Giving Birth to Agripreneurs (Partha Sarathy Adhya and Suresh Kumar Sahoo 2022). The article contains the conceptual framework on agri tech startup opportunities in Indian agriculture. Agri-tech start-ups are successful in improving supply chains, but the progress is slow. Thus, the government should come forward to encourage and facilitate the entrepreneurs by providing necessary facilitations like infrastructure, financial support and proper rules and regulation is the conclusion drawn from the study.

Assessing a digital agri tech start-up landscape and identifying potential opportunities for partnerships and funding (Himadri Sikhar Swain, M Chandrakumar, D Murugananthi and G Vanitha) has studied about the grant opportunities of agriculture technology startups which include angel funding, seed funding, series A, B, C for different stages of startups.

Karnataka Startups policy 2022-27, The policy provides the details of the government schemes and policies towards the growth and development of the overall startup industry in the state.

Start-up India: Opportunities and Challenges” (Sumit Mishra) has elaborated the lifecycle of startup and also the startup financial life cycle. The study provides insights of opportunities for startups.

International

IGNITE your corporate innovation: insights from setting up an ag-tech start-up accelerator INDUSTRY SPEAKS (Aidan J. Connolly a, Justin Turnerb, and Alexa D. Potockic) has given an ecosystem for startup followed by innovation in agriculture, the role of corporate accelerators. INGNITE explains a study by All Tech as per its learning has given as such:- Intention-Define your intentions and decide if an accelerator is right for your company. Group-Create a special group or team to design and oversee the program. Neighborhood-Provide the cohort with an off-site neighborhood locale for uninhibited focus. Independence-Ensure the start-up engagement is independent of day to day commercial efforts. Transparency-Be transparent with the cohort on the goals and opportunities of the program. Expertise-Recruit the best experts and specialists you can, internally and externally to run the program and mentor start-ups.

A Lubrication of the Agri tech startups in India (Dr. Manisha Sharma and Ms Simrandeep Kaur Randhawa) has explained agriculture with more than 58 % of Population towards the Indian Economy. A comparative yield analysis is made among the agri tech sub sectors. Followed with this analysis the challenges of the agri tech startups are being explained.

Constructing agri-food for finance: startups, venture capital and food future imaginaries(Sarah Ruth Sippell, Moritz Dolinga). This paper has studied the impact of financial imaginaries, and investigated investment motivations. A detailed examination of the challenges faced by agri-food tech startups, including market competition, regulatory hurdles, and the need for sustainable practices.

An Assessment of Competitiveness of Technology-Based Startups in India(Krishna Satyanarayanan, deepak Chandrashekar and Bala Subramanya Mungila Hillemane)The study utilized the **Cox proportional hazards model** for statistical analysis to deduce the factors impacting the survival of technology-based startups. This model is particularly suited for survival analysis, allowing the researchers to assess the time until an event occurs.

Ideas and Methods of Lean and Agile startup in the VUCA era(Chengbin Wang, Yongyan Fang and Chuanfeng Liu) A highly uncertain startup environment is studied through VUCA which adopts the Lean and Agile Startup method by using the Business Model Canvas and iterative tool to develop the software by improving the convenience for the ventures.

Objectives:

1. To classify the volatility and uncertainty of agri tech startups in India throughout its lifecycle.
2. To identify the complexity and ambiguity of agri tech startups in india.

Methodology:

The study is about Indian agri tech startups. The study is descriptive in nature. The data collected for the research is secondary data from the published research papers, thesis, journals, discussion papers, and websites.

Startup stages:

The stages of agri tech startups have steps involved describing the process of establishing and sustaining in the market. These stages include:- Pre seed stage, Seed stage, early stage, Growth stage, Last stage.(MANAGE, Discussion paper, 2019).

The early stage includes the pre seed stage and seed stage. At this stage the company would offer the products and services to the customers with a new innovative idea of the startup.

The growth stage includes the development of the Agri-tech startup sustaining the customers, investing on the strategies, trying to uphold itself from the competition. This is the maturity stage of the startup life cycle.

The last stage after maturity is when the startup is struggling to exist in the market or turns into unicorn.

Analysing the challenges of Agri-tech start-ups alongside with the stages-VUCA approach.

Stages	Volatility	Complexity	Uncertainty	Ambiguity
Pre seed stage	Market positioning	Technology adoptions	Funding	Idea generation
Seed stage	Customer acceptance.	Supply chain	Seasonal and wether dependency	Issues on regulation
Growth stage	High capital investment	Innovations in strategies	Competitors market	Data and analytics
Last stage	Sustainability concerns	Market access	IPO, Funding	Fear of existence

Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity, The VUCA approach are the hurdles of agri tech startups facing during their journey of establishment, set up and sustainability. These challenges can be analysed under the stages of the startups relating to agri tech.

Pre-seed stage:

An early stage, where the product will be yet to take birth from the innovators effort. The stage involves creation of idea, obtaining funds, setting up the business. Generation of idea requires innovation and creative thoughts which lead the product or service into attraction by the customers. The idea is brought into existence when there are require level of funding to adopt the techniques of innovation. Technology adoptions are complex as the generation is moving to 5.0 which include Robotics, AI[Artificial Intelligence], IOT[Internet of Things], Big data analytics, Block chain, Augmented reality(Adhya, Partha and Sahoo). The entrepreneur should obtain the knowledge of the technology and let them adapt to the Start-up. As the stage is creating a base line for the product to enter the market, obtaining the

market position is volatile, as the product is new to the market. The customers try to analyse the innovation and the benefits of the product.(MANAGE, discussion paper 2019).

Seed stage:

The product is created an existence, identity and trying to move up for sales and profit. In seed stage the efforts of the entrepreneur is not on establishment but on movement to existence and sustainability. The customers are the illiterate farmers who need to be taught from the scratch. Customers are the target group to be attracted. The products once reaches the customers, they study and analyse whether the product to be repurchased or to stop purchasing. The acceptance of the products is volatile and need to be fixed up with the proper strategies. The volatility of the customer acceptance is due to the technology adoptions for the farmers who were following traditional format of farming and now has to shift the type of farming. Reaching the customer through a proper supply chain is also very essential. Middlemen acts in Agriculture, these middlemen to be avoided. Agri-tech start-ups, few start-ups face water and seasonal issue with reference to the type of product [Fasal, Sencrop]. The uncertainty exists in the seasonal and weather conditions, which need to be considered for development of the product position. The funding will be increased to develop the product but the regulations can be a hurdle for the further movement of star-up.[Crowdfunding, Angel investors, incubators] (MANAGE, discussion paper 2019).

Growth stage:

The Start-up is grabbed the position in the minds of the customer, now the innovator should adopt some strategies to retain the importance of the product. Agri- tech start-up is an innovation of agriculture where the traditional agriculture is replaced with technology, Knowledge of adoption of the product is provided for the farmers/ customers. At this stage the competitors emerge by following the same technique. Same product will be available in the market by the competitors. The Agri tech start-up has to follow new innovation strategies to differentiate from the competitors. Creation of competitors is uncertain but the Start-ups has to find out a solution of strategies which is complex. To adopt creation of strategies a proper research to be conducted. Having a research team is high budget, for which the capital to be obtained. The Start-up tries to obtain investment but the guarantee of existence will be wavering. Agri-tech start-ups struggle to move from this step due to less research on existence, data analytics. Analysing the data is done to know about the Start-up and product acceptance by the Customers. The data will provide the feedback of the users and also the reviews which will help the Start-ups to adopt.

Last stage:

This stage includes maturing, matured and post maturing stage of Star-ups. The stage has two options for the Start-ups, one either to re-innovate the idea of to close the Start-up. The stage suffers a lot for sustainability of the Agri-tech start-up. This struggle is due to the increase of competitors, lack of research, movement to higher level of management. The obtaining fund can be done by issuing of IPO in the market. This involves strong foundation of existence of the start-up. The Agri –tech start-up is an element of sustainability. The sustainability of the start-up is also very complex, uncertain and volatile. The entrepreneurs have to make efforts for the sustainability concerns by gaining the market and customer support.

Conclusion:

The stages of the Agri-tech start-up are as similar to the other kind of start-up, but the VUCA approach has a difference. The Agri-tech start-up faces many challenges since its creation to its existence and sustainability. The Challenges are addressed with the solutions by government, incubation centres. Though many initiatives and funding process are setup by the government and PPP Agri-tech startups are struggling to exist in the market. Its 10 years hence the first Agri-tech start-up emerged in India but not even 1[one] has turned to unicorn. Agri-tech start-ups, these are the conversion of the traditional agriculture into technological equipped manner by solving the problems of the farmers at all levels. Let the sustainability concerns work on supporting Agri-tech start-ups and the innovation of the products. The study can be further expanded by analysing the VUCA approach among the Agri-tech start-ups which gives the clear approach of the government support and the incubation centres on the development of the start-ups.

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